

Exploring AI's Impact on Museums: Key Takeaways from the Open Science Working Group

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On Monday, March 17, 2025, Austria's federal museums gathered to discuss the role of AI in the museum world. The working group, "Open Science¹," delved into the positive and negative implications of AI, tackling philosophical, ethical, legal, and practical questions. The workshop provided valuable insights into best practices and real-world examples from museums. The EOSC SOA also joined the discussion, highlighting its initiative and the potential for future collaboration. Curious to learn more? Click here for the full recap!

AI Policies – an International Perspective

The workshop kicked off with opening remarks from Katrin Vohland, CEO of the NHMW, followed by an insightful presentation by Christian Huemer, Head of the Belvedere Research Centre, who shared an international perspective on the intersection of AI and museums. He noted that, surprisingly, there is very little available on this topic for museums in general although there appear to be many internal Working Groups focusing on the topics at hand. Additionally, some institutions, such as the Austrian National Library (ÖNB), have developed their own in-house guidelines. To date, though, there are no overarching frameworks that address the use of AI tools in areas like

education or research as there are challenges to be met with respect to the diversity of applications and the willingness of the federal museums to pay for individual AI applications.

AI Policies in Federal Museums

Next, AI policies - namely those of the ÖNB were presented. Back in 2024, it adopted corresponding guidelines emphasizing key principles such as data protection, transparency, clear labeling of AI usage, and preventing manipulation. It also prioritized trust, quality assurance, fairness, inclusion, information literacy, sustainability, and collaboration. The guidelines aim at its own employees and various partners. Additionally, the ÖNB offers its employees training courses.

¹ For further information on Open Science in Austria's federal museums, see https://www.nhm-wien.ac.at/jart/prj3/nhm-resp/data/uploads/Verlag/OS_BM_Broschuere_2022_final.pdf

Group Discussions

Afterward, participants engaged in small group discussions focused on ethical, legal, and practical considerations. In addition, one group was given the freedom to explore topics of their own choosing:

Guidelines related to ethics and law should consider several key aspects: the review and selection of licenses (which should be institutional rather than private), risk management, and ensuring appropriate awareness through training. Other important factors include how AI tool usage should be cited, the risks associated with training data, such as bias and its implications, and, finally, the role of users, who should bear ultimate responsibility, regardless of the specific application.

From an economic perspective, it is crucial to carefully examine and select different providers. In practical museum settings, it's important to consider that the time saved through AI tools may not always outweigh the additional effort required to implement them. Participants in the small group discussions also agreed that dedicated points of contact with relevant expertise are necessary for addressing these topics.

The EOSC Support Office Austria

Finally, Bernd Saurugger offered a comprehensive overview of the EOSC

SOA, covering its vision, activities, achievements, and opportunities for participation. He also highlighted the potential benefits of becoming a member, sparking a discussion on potential synergies - regarding repositories or competence development.

Conclusions

Finally, the importance of the meeting was recognized: It should be possible to establish overarching guidelines like those of the ÖNB. For individual tools, general criteria could be valuable (e.g., concerning security, costs, or effectiveness), offering both federal and other museums a key reference point for how these issues can be addressed within their specific institutions.

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